

The mobility of protons in urea nitrate crystals changes the electroneutrality of cadmium oxide and causes the displacement of Cd^{2+} ions which in turn combine with the nitrate present at the interphase resulting in the formation of cadmium nitrate. These steps occurring at the points of contact of the two solids are soon followed by the bulk reaction because of the movement of nitrate ions from the bulk which in turn takes place due to the concentration gradient set up by the removal of nitrate ions at the surface. Thus protonation of cadmium oxide as a result of the mobility of hydrogen ions from urea nitrate leaves behind urea at the end of the reaction. In the beginning due to nucleation process cadmium nitrate is formed in the vicinity of the original interface which soon spreads to the entire bulk on account of small particle size of the reactants. Since the volume of the particle is very small compared to its surface area, the nucleation process would completely consume the total volume of the reactants.

References

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Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Function of Zn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenoneanil

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IN continuation of our previous communications^{2,3} herein, we describe potentiometric studies on chelates of 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenoneanil (HCBA) with Zn(II) and Cd(II) in 60% v/v dioxan water media at $\mu=0.1M$ at 25°, 30° and 35°.

Experimental

The expanded scale pH meter of Systronic with a wide range (0.01 pH) glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone anil was synthesised by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone with aniline. It was crystallised from alcohol ; m. p. 148°.

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. The potentiometric titration was carried out in an inert atmosphere using carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution and the constant ionic strength was maintained by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solution. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{4,5} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹ has been applied to determine the protonation constants of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log K values were computed by various computational methods as summarised in Table-1. The linear plots of $\log \frac{\bar{n}A}{1-\bar{n}A}$ vs B for ligand and formation curves of Zn(II) and Cd(II) chelates are shown in figures 1, 2, and 3 respectively.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\frac{\bar{n}A}{1-\bar{n}A}$ vs B of 2-Hydroxy-5-Chlorobenzophenoneanil at 25°, 30° and 35°.

Fig. 2. Formation curves of Zn(HCBA)₂ at 25°, 30° and 35°.